

AUTOMATING THE DERIVATION OF EQUATIONS FOR 1D MASS-SPRING-DAMPER MODELS IN MATLAB

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Abstract *It is common to spend considerable time writing and implementing equations for 1D mass-spring-damper dynamics models when teaching the simulation of system dynamics using MATLAB ode solvers. These models typically involve masses, springs, and dashpots. In this paper, the authors present a systematic symbolic calculus approach to automate the process of deriving the necessary equations from the model and first principles. This approach utilizes a table, similar to the connectivity table used in finite element analysis. In this paper, the process is limited to 1D cases but can be used for complex systems by extending the symbolic definitions and equations accordingly. These equations are central to the time integration function, such as the ode45 function in MATLAB. This method streamlines the process of quickly writing and testing different models, reducing frustration caused by minor typographical errors that often arise. First, a basic 1D dynamics model is defined using a simple example. Next, a straightforward MATLAB symbolic code that automatically generates the equations for the subroutine called by the Ordinary Differential Equations (ODE) solver is introduced. Finally, the system's response over time is obtained, including the positions and velocities of the system for the given initial conditions.*

1. INTRODUCTION

There are several reasons why one should care about mass-spring systems. In fact, a wide range of engineering problems can be modelled using simple mass-spring systems. The mass-spring-damper model, which consists of discrete masses connected by springs and dampers, is particularly effective for simulating various phenomena. Not only mechanical, it also has an electrical-mechanical analogy, which makes it valuable for solving several other types of problems.

By applying Newton's second law to the forces and dynamic equilibria of the point masses—including the forces exerted by the springs and any external forces—one can derive a second-order differential equations system (as outlined in [1]). These equations can generally be solved using symbolic calculus for simple cases or with ODE solvers for more complex systems. Even though in this paper, only simple systems were considered to obtain the motion equation recurring to Newton's second law, for systems that are more complicated one may use the Lagrange-Hamilton principle.

Creating and implementing equations of motion for 1D mass-spring-damper models is a common exercise in simulating basic system dynamics, particularly in educational contexts. However, this process can be time-consuming and susceptible to minor errors. While there are studies [2,3] that explore the derivation of dynamic models, such as in the robotics industry and car suspension systems, the authors did not find any literature directly addressing the here proposed automatic derivation method. Nonetheless, one assumes that similar efforts may have likely been undertaken.

In this paper, the authors propose a systematic approach to automate the derivation of the necessary equations from the model and first principles. This method utilizes a simple table, similar to the connectivity table used in finite element analysis [4] and the MATLAB programming capacities. While in this paper, this symbolic method is limited to 1D translational cases, it can be extended to more complex systems by adapting the symbolic definitions and equations.

This approach streamlines the process of writing and testing different models, reducing the frustration associated with typo errors that appear when equations are manually coded. The derived equations are compatible with the MATLAB symbolic toolbox, enabling efficient symbolic computations. Additionally, the same equations are compatible with MATLAB's ODE solvers, such as the `ode45` function, allowing for numerical approximations of the system's behaviour.

The structure of the paper is as follows: After this introductory section, the fundamental concepts are presented in section 2. Next, in section 3, a basic 1D dynamics model is defined using an example for which the equations are derived manually and using MATLAB symbolic code that automatically generates the equations. Then it is shown in section 4, for an example of a simplified $\frac{1}{4}$ car suspension (i.e., only one wheel) how to obtain the system's response over time, including position and velocity for a set of given initial conditions. The paper demonstrates how to use the derived equations for: i) symbolic computation to obtain an analytical solution; and ii) for numerical approximation using the ODE solver. In section 5, it is presented another example, with more masses and connections, to illustrate the potential

of the proposed method. Finally, in section 6, the main conclusions are presented.

2. FUNDAMENTALS

Mass-spring-damper models, as previously mentioned, consist of discrete masses connected by springs and dampers, also discretized for two-point connections. These systems are typically discrete, meaning that the masses are concentrated at specific points, with springs and dashpots (dampers) connecting them.

The forces applied to springs follow Hooke's Law, which states that the force exerted by a spring is proportional to the displacement from its equilibrium length:

$$F_{spring} = -k \cdot (L - L_0) \quad (1)$$

Here, k is the spring constant, L is the current length of the spring, and L_0 is the natural (unstretched) length or rest length of the spring. The force is directed opposite to the displacement, indicating that the spring attempts to restore the system to its equilibrium position.

Dashpots are components that introduce a viscoelastic damping behaviour between the masses. The force exerted by a dashpot is proportional to the rate of change of displacement (velocity), and it opposes the motion:

$$F_{dashpot} = -c \cdot \frac{dL}{dt} \quad (2)$$

where c is the dashpot constant, and dL/dt represents the velocity of the length variation. Dashpots model friction or energy dissipation, such as the action of a car shock absorber or muscle tissue.

To derive the equations of motion for these systems, one first separates the system in several free-body diagrams (one for each mass) and sum the forces acting on each mass, including any external forces $F_{external}$. Using Newton's second law of motion, one obtains the differential equations that govern the motion of the masses in the system.

$$\sum F = m \cdot a = m \cdot \frac{d^2y}{dt^2} \quad (3)$$

where the sum of forces F is the net force, m is the mass, and a is the acceleration of the respective mass. The acceleration is the second derivative of displacement with respect to time, and this will lead to a second-order differential equation with the dependent variable y (displacement) and the independent variable t (time).

The system's parameters include the masses m_i , spring constants k_j , and dashpot constants c_j . To fully define the system response, two initial conditions are required for each mass: its initial displacement from a reference point and its initial velocity.

The system may be either unforced, where motion is driven solely by the initial conditions, or it may be forced, with an external excitation $f(t)$. In the unforced case, any motion arises purely from the initial conditions, which may involve the springs being stretched or compressed at $t=0$.

In the next section is illustrated, with one example, how the equation of motion is obtained for the system. It typically results in a linear constant-coefficient second-order ODE.

3. OBTAINING THE SYSTEM OF EQUATIONS

The following mass-spring-dashpot system represents a simplified model of the suspension system of one quarter of an automobile. The mass 1 is the corresponding part from the wheel and suspension and mass 2 is the corresponding part of the vehicle. The input to the system is the time-varying displacement $y_0(t)$ that represents the road position along the time. It is assumed permanent contact of tire with the road. The shock absorber is composed by its massless spring k_2 and massless dashpot c_2 . The vehicle tire is represented by the spring k_1 with negligible damping. This example was adopted from [5].

Figure 1. Mass-spring-dashpot system representation of a simplified model of the suspension system of one quarter of an automobile.

3.1. Analytical procedure done manually

Applying Newton's law of motion to the two masses, according to their free-body diagram (see Fig. 2), yields the following system of equations.

$$\begin{cases} m_1 \frac{d^2 y_1}{dt^2} = -k_1 * (y_1 - y_0 - L_{01}) + k_2 * (y_2 - y_1 - L_{02}) + c_2 * \left(\frac{dy_2}{dt} - \frac{dy_1}{dt} \right) \\ m_2 \frac{d^2 y_2}{dt^2} = -k_2 * (y_2 - y_1 - L_{02}) - c_2 * \left(\frac{dy_2}{dt} - \frac{dy_1}{dt} \right) \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Figure 2. Free-body diagrams for each mass and its external forces

The symbolic procedure allows to input the equations as second ODE.

3.2. Automatizing the obtaining of motion equations procedure with MATLAB

The procedure described in section 3.1 to obtain the equations from the Newton's law of motion to the two masses, according to their free-body diagram, may be implemented computationally to automatically produce the respective equations.

For it, the following code was implemented.

It start by inputing the Number of Connections of each mass $M(i)$, in this case are 2 for mass 1 and 1 for mass 2.

Next, one defines the connectivity table in the following format by line $\text{Table}(i,:)=[iM,jM,iK,iC]$; which corresponds to conectivities of mass 'i' with other masses 'j', and corresponding index of de spring and of the dashpot, if present. The following code is the result of this implementation.

```
clear all; close all; clc
%=====
Orientation='V' %use H=horizontal Ox or V=Vertical Oy
%=====
NumberConnectionsM(1)=2; %% 1 springs and (1spring+1dashpots) NumberOfLinesInTable
NumberConnectionsM(2)=1; %% 1 (1spring+ 1dashpots)
%
n1=NumberConnectionsM(1); % 2
n2=n1+NumberConnectionsM(2); % 3
pointer=[n1,n2]
%
```

```
Table=[1,0,1,0;... % conectivities i j knumber cnumber
      1,2,2,2;... %% 4 means k4 assembled (pretension may be included)
      2,1,2,2];... %% repetition of 2,3,0,2;
```

These are all the inputs needed to obtain the equations of the system. It also considers the two orientation possibilities of the system, all in Ox direction ('H') or all in Oy direction ('V').

```
%=====
if Orientation=='H'
    strvar='x'
elseif Orientation=='V'
    strvar='y'
else
    display('Orientation used is not implemented')
end
```

The numerical procedure requires that all the equations be of first order differential type, so one needs to reduce them to a system of first order equations. Here, one decided to have first all the velocities and after, all the accelerations terms. Based on (4), the following system of first order ODE are obtained.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{dy_1}{dt} = y_3 \\ \frac{dy_2}{dt} = y_4 \\ \frac{dy_3}{dt} = \frac{-k_1 * (y_1 - y_0 - L_{01}) + k_2 * (y_2 - y_1 - L_{02}) + c_2 * (\frac{dy_2}{dt} - \frac{dy_1}{dt})}{m_1} \\ \frac{dy_4}{dt} = \frac{-k_2 * (y_2 - y_1 - L_{02}) - c_2 * (\frac{dy_2}{dt} - \frac{dy_1}{dt})}{m_2} \end{array} \right. \quad (5)$$

For it, the following code is implemented.

```
%=====
nmasses=size(pointer,2) % number of mass (bodies)
%=====
for mm=1:nmasses
str= horzcat('d',strvar,(',', num2str(mm), ',1)=' ,strvar,(',', num2str(mm+nmasses),
');')
eq(mm,1)={str};
end%
```

For each mass, the code goes through the Table lines and the corresponding force terms are added to a string (in the code is the variable *str*) using MATLAB commands *horzcats*. First, it uses information of column 3 of the Table, i.e. for the springs.

```

for mm=1:nmasses
%=====
% define lines of table for this mass == from iline to kline
if mm~=1
iline=pointer(mm-1)+1; % next line is pointer(mm-1)+1
else % where pointer=[n1,n2,n3];
iline=1; % avoid index zero inside pointer(mm-1)
end %
kline=pointer(mm);
%=====
%str='('; % needed
str= horzcat('d',strvar, '(', num2str(nmasses+mm), ',1)=(')
%=====
for ii=iline:kline
if (Table(ii,3)~=0)
%===== SPRINGS =====
if (Table(ii,1)>Table(ii,2))
Lsignal='-';
strX=sprintf(['%s %s%i%s%i %s%s'], 'Because assumes: ', ...
strvar, Table(ii,1), '>', strvar, Table(ii,2), ' => ', Lsignal);
else
Lsignal='+';
strX=sprintf(['%s %s%i%s%i %s%s'], 'Because assumes:', ...
strvar, Table(ii,1), '<', strvar, Table(ii,2), ' => ', Lsignal);
end
display(strX);
aux=horzcat('-k(', num2str(Table(ii,3)), ')*(', strvar, '(', num2str(Table(ii,1)), ')-'
', ...
strvar, '(', num2str(Table(ii,2)), ')', ...
Lsignal, 'L0(', num2str(Table(ii,3)), ')')');
str=horzcat(str, aux);
end %if(Table(ii,3)~=0)
%=====

```

After, it uses information of column 4 of the Table, i.e. for the dashpots.

```

%=====DASHPOTS=====
if (Table(ii,4)~=0)
aux=horzcat('-
c(', num2str(Table(ii,4)), ')*(d', strvar, '(', num2str(Table(ii,1)), ')-'
d', strvar, '(', num2str(Table(ii,2)), ')')');
str=horzcat(str, aux);
end

```

```

%=====
end %ii
str=horzcat(str,')/m(',num2str(mm),');');
eq(nmasses+mm,1)={str};
end% mm%=====

```

Finally, it write the equations to the display and to a txt file.

```

%eq
g0=[eq(1:nmasses)]
gy=[eq(nmasses+1:2*nmasses)]
display('Remark: It assumes i>j ==> xi>xj and signals of forces are according to
it')
display('Remark: Remove any x(0) replace by x0 value or expression and dx(0) as 0
or expression')
writecell([g0; gy], 'C_tab.txt', 'Delimiter', 'tab')

```

Running this code with the input data, one gets the required equations in the display as well as in the file C_tab.txt.

$$\begin{aligned}
 dy(1,1) &= y(3); \\
 dy(2,1) &= y(4); \\
 dy(3,1) &= (-k(1)*(y(1)-y(0)-L0(1))-k(2)*(y(1)-y(2)+L0(2))-c(2)*(dy(1)-dy(2)))/m(1); \\
 dy(4,1) &= (-k(2)*(y(2)-y(1)-L0(2))-c(2)*(dy(2)-dy(1)))/m(2);
 \end{aligned}$$

(4)

These equations are correct, see equations (3).

4. SOLVING THE SYSTEM OF DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS

4.1. Using symbolic computation toolbox of the MATLAB

For simple systems, it may be solved using MATLAB's the symbolic computation toolbox, as exemplified by the following code.

```

clear all; clc

syms u1(t) u2(t) u3(t) u4(t) t

m = [110; 1900];
k = [136; 16];
c = [0; 176];
%===== Put Eqs here =====
ode1 = diff(u1) == u3;
ode2 = diff(u2) == u4;
ode3 = diff(u3) == (k(1)*.05*sin(3*pi*t)-c(2)*(u3-u4)-k(2)*(u1-u2)-k(1)*u1)/m(1);
ode4 = diff(u4) == (c(2)*(u3-u4)+k(2)*(u1-u2))/m(2);
odes = [ode1; ode2; ode3; ode4]

```

```

cond1 = u1(0) == 0;
cond2 = u2(0) == 0;
cond3 = u3(0) == 0;
cond4 = u4(0) == 0;
conds = [cond1; cond2; cond3; cond4];
[u1Sol(t),u2Sol(t),u3Sol(t),u4Sol(t)] = dsolve(odes,conds)

VpaU1=vpa(u1Sol); tt=0:0.01:5; YY=matlabFunction(VpaU1); yy=real(YY(tt));
plot(tt,yy); hold on
VpaU2=vpa(u2Sol); tt=0:0.01:5; YY2=matlabFunction(VpaU2); yy2=real(YY2(tt));
plot(tt,yy2)
grid on
legend('u1Sol','u2Sol','Location','best')
title('Analytical Solution')

```

The code generates the following plot (Fig. 3) for the position of the masses. It presents the idea and coding, but it is only a first quick prototype. This helps teachers, but to learn one recommends that students practice for several examples. Animations were considered out of scope of this manuscript but are also important for the analysis.

Figure 3. Plot of positions in time obtained with the Symbolic Toolbox

This is the expected plot, where the wheel (u1) oscillates more, dissipating energy, while the chassis (u2) oscillates less.

4.2. Using numerical computation with ODEs of the MATLAB

In general, it may be solved using numerical MATLAB's integration of ODEs. The following code exemplifies it.

```
clear all; clc
m = [110; 1900];
k = [136; 16];
c = [0; 176];
opts = odeset(RelTol=1e-8,AbsTol=1e-8);
[t, y] = ode45 (@spring, [0 5], [0,0,0,0],opts, m, k, c);
plot (t, y(:, 1), t, y(:, 2));
```

```
function yp = spring (t, y, m, k, c)
yp = zeros(4,1);
yp(1) = y(3);
yp(2) = y(4);
yp(3) = (k(1)*.05*sin(3*pi*t)-c(2)*(y(3)-y(4))-k(2)*(y(1)-y(2))-k(1)*y(1))/m(1);
yp(4) = (c(2)*(y(3)-y(4))+k(2)*(y(1)-y(2)))/m(2);
```

The above script runs `ode45` with the function *spring* and produces the following result (Fig. 4), which is practically equal to the one obtained with the Symbolic Toolbox.

Figure 4. Plot of positions in time obtained with `ode45` with function *spring*.

5. EXAMPLE WITH MORE CONNECTIONS

To illustrate the potential of the method to generate the motion equations, let us consider another example. In principle, one can have as many finite masses and connections as necessary.

Figure 5. A three masses system

To obtain the equations of motion for the system of the Fig.5, one needs to give the orientation (in this case is horizontal) and the connectivity table. The mass 1 has three connections, because the spring 1 and dashpot 1 count as one. The masses 2 and 3 have two connections each.

```
clear all; close all; clc
%=====
Orientation='H' %use H=horizontal Ox or V=Vertical Oy
NumberConnectionsM1=3; %% 2 springs and (1spring+ 1dashpots) NumberOfLinesInTable
NumberConnectionsM2=2; %% 1 springs and (1spring+ 1dashpots)
NumberConnectionsM3=2; %% 1 springs and (1spring+ 1dashpots)
n1=NumberConnectionsM1; % 4
n2=n1+NumberConnectionsM2; % 7
n3=n2+NumberConnectionsM3; % 10
pointer=[n1,n2,n3]
Table=[1,0,1,1;... % conectivities i j knumber cnumber
       1,3,4,0;... %% 4 means k4 assembled (pretension may be included)
       1,2,2,0;... % conectivities i j knumber cnumber
       2,1,2,0;... %repetition of 1,2,2,0
       2,3,3,3;... % conectivities i j knumber cnumber
       3,1,4,0;... %% repetition 4 means k4 assembled
       3,2,3,3]; %repetition of 2,3,3,0; %3,2,0,3
```

These are all the necessary inputs to obtain the equations for the system. It also

considers the orientation of the system, in this case are all in Ox direction ('H').

Running the code described in the section 3.2 with the orientation information and the Table given, it produces the motion equations of the system, in the display as well as in the file C_tab.txt. The equations obtained in this case are:

$$\begin{aligned}
 dx(1,1) &= x(4); \\
 dx(2,1) &= x(5); \\
 dx(3,1) &= x(6); \\
 dx(4,1) &= (-k(1)*(x(1)-x(0)-L0(1))-c(1)*(dx(1)-dx(0))-k(4)*(x(1)-x(3)+L0(4))-k(2)*(x(1)-x(2)+L0(2)))/m(1); \\
 dx(5,1) &= (-k(2)*(x(2)-x(1)-L0(2))-k(3)*(x(2)-x(3)+L0(3))-c(3)*(dx(2)-dx(3)))/m(2); \\
 dx(6,1) &= (-k(4)*(x(3)-x(1)-L0(4))-k(3)*(x(3)-x(2)-L0(3))-c(3)*(dx(3)-dx(2)))/m(3);
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{5}$$

Like in section 4.2, these equations can now be solved using MATLAB's numerical integration of ODEs. The following code exemplifies it.

```

function [] = MyTest()
%=====
m=[15; 25;5]; X0=[1.; 1.5;1.6]; V0=[0.; 0.;0.];
k=[23; 25;16;30]; L0=[1; 0.5;0.1;0.5]; c=[30; 2; 2; 5];
t0=0; tf=20;
%=====
[t, y] = ode45 (@ode_Ndof, [t0 tf], [X0',V0'],[], m, k, c, L0);
figure(1)
plot(t, y(:, 1), t, y(:, 2),t, y(:, 3));
legend('position1','position2','position3')
figure(2)
plot(t, y(:, 4), t, y(:, 5),t, y(:, 6));
legend('veloc1','veloc2','veloc3')
%=====
function dx = ode_Ndof(t,x, m, k, c,L0)
%
x0=0; dx0=0; %fixed on the left
dx(1,1)=x(4);
dx(2,1)=x(5);
dx(3,1)=x(6);
dx(4,1)=(-k(1)*(x(1)-x0-L0(1))-c(1)*(dx(1)-dx0)-k(4)*(x(1)-x(3)+L0(4))-k(2)*(x(1)-x(2)+L0(2)))/m(1);
dx(5,1)= (-k(2)*(x(2)-x(1)-L0(2))-k(3)*(x(2)-x(3)+L0(3))-c(3)*(dx(2)-dx(3)))/m(2);
dx(6,1)= (-k(4)*(x(3)-x(1)-L0(4))-k(3)*(x(3)-x(2)-L0(3))-c(3)*(dx(3)-dx(2)))/m(3);
end
end

```

The above function runs ode45 with the function *spring* and produces the following result (Fig. 6).

Figure 6. Plot of positions in time obtained with ode45 with function *MyTest*.

Note that the system has in its initial position the spring 4 in traction, while the others are in their rest length position. When the system is released from its initial position, it undergoes into free vibration and is damped by the two dashpots up to the final equilibrium position. Therefore, body 3 starts by moving back, which is the expected behaviour. The example illustrates how the automatic derivation of motion equations can be applied to help with these analyses.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper is presented a tool that automatically derives the equations of motion for mass-spring-damper systems based on Newton's Second Law. The method requires only a connectivity table detailing the connections between masses, springs, and dampers. Initially, the approach is limited to one-dimensional translational motion with external forces or unconstrained motion.

This paper introduces the concept and provides a basic prototype of the code, though it is still in its early stages. For instance, the connectivity table can be enhanced to eliminate redundant connections when multiple masses are involved, reducing any repetitive input. With further refinement, the tool has the potential to automatically generate all the necessary code for system analysis, including reading input data for springs, dampers, masses, and initial conditions from an external file.

This method aims to assist educators in teaching complex systems involving multiple masses, springs, and dampers. However, it is recommended that students first practice deriving the equations of motion manually to deepen their understanding. While animations would be valuable for visualizing these systems, they were beyond the scope of this work.

To solve the equations of motion, one initially used MATLAB's symbolic tools, followed by the ode45 Runge-Kutta numerical integration method to compute the system's response. A comparison of the results confirmed the accuracy of the approach.

In conclusion, while obtaining analytical solutions is important, engineers are typically more interested in the qualitative characteristics of the solutions, such as resonance and beats. This method provides a quick way to assess these important system behaviours.

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